

THE ROLE OF MUKHAMMAD RAKHIMOKHAN II (FERUZ) IN THE KHORAZM MIGHTY MOVEMENT

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Abstract: This thesis examines the influence of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II on the formation of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm. In the second half of the 19th century, Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II, the ruler of the Khanate of Khiva, took an active part not only in state administration, but also in cultural and educational reforms. His attention to science, literature and culture laid the foundation for the emergence and spread of modernist ideas in society. The article analyzes the historical conditions of the development of the Jadidist movement and the policy of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II in this regard. Historical sources and scientific literature were used during the research.

Key words: Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II, Jadidist movement, Khorezm, Khiva Khanate, cultural reforms, enlightenment, historical conditions.

Introduction:

The second half of the 19th century is distinguished as a period of rapid development of cultural and educational reforms in Central Asia. Khorezm, with its rich cultural heritage and historical traditions, became one of the important centers during this period. The ruler of the Khanate of Khiva, Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II (*Feruz*), along with strengthening the state administration, made a great contribution to the emergence and development of the ideas of enlightenment and modernism in the society.

The Jadidism movement aimed to promote new ideas and ideas aimed at the development of enlightenment, education and culture in Muslim societies at that time. The formation and development of this movement in Khorezm is largely related to the reforms of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II. During his reign, he paid attention to culture, science and literature and helped to establish modern educational institutions and libraries. Therefore, studying the political and cultural activities of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II is important for understanding the formation process of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm.

The social, economic and cultural changes that took place in the Khiva Khanate in the second half of the 19th century laid the groundwork for the emergence of the Jadidist movement. During the reign of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II (*Feruz*), interest in education, culture and science increased in the

country. He was one of the leading state leaders of his time and took an active part in both areas - state administration and cultural and educational reforms. This situation was an important factor in the formation of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm.

Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II, first of all, during his reign, attached great importance to the strengthening of the state. He introduced administrative and economic reforms to ensure fair governance. At the same time, he paid attention to culture and literature, and through his poems written under the pseudonym Feruz, he preached to his contemporaries the pursuit of enlightenment and knowledge. Khan gathered advanced intellectuals and enlighteners around him and contributed to the formation of a scientific and cultural environment in Khiva.

In order to support cultural and educational reforms in the country, Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II paid great attention to the opening of new schools and madrasahs, and the establishment of libraries. He was especially in favor of introducing a new teaching system. This helped to spread the ideas of modernism in the society. In the schools and madrasahs opened during the reign of Rakhim Khan II, not only religious sciences, but also secular sciences began to be taught. This new educational system was one of the main principles of the modernist movement and encouraged the development of science and enlightenment in society.

In the preparation of the article, archival documents, historical sources and written monuments of the time of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II were used. Research works and monographs on the history of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm were also addressed. These materials allow a more complete study of the activities of Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II in the field of education, culture and enlightenment. On this basis, the khan's contribution to the formation of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm was analyzed.

During the discussion, it was found that the reforms and initiatives implemented by Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II during his time had a positive impact on the development of Jadidism ideas. The success of this movement, in turn, accelerated the formation of new enlightened values in Khorezm and the processes of renewal in various spheres of social life. Thus, the cultural and educational reforms of Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II played an important role in increasing the intellectual potential of the society and directing the people towards knowledge and enlightenment. His initiatives increased the interest in

modern knowledge in the society, created the ground for the emergence of enlightenment and new thinking.

The main reforms of Feruz in the field of education were related to:

1. Establishment of new-style schools: During his reign, Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II paid great attention to the establishment of new-style schools along with traditional religious schools. As an example, "*Feruz Khan was also a devotee of education who built a 2-story madrasa named after him in front of the Old Arch of Khiva in 1871*" [9, p. 122]. These schools were one of the main principles of the Jadidist movement, and secular sciences were taught in them along with religious knowledge. The teaching of arithmetic, geography, history, natural science and other worldly sciences in schools of the new method formed new knowledge and views in the society. This became the foundation for scientific and technical development and social changes in the future.

2. Development of libraries and scientific and educational environment: During the reign of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II, the establishment of libraries and attention to science was another important reform in the field of education. He created a large library in his palace, where he collected books not only on religious, but also on secular sciences. A scientific and educational environment was formed around the scientists and educators who worked in this library, which contributed to the development of new approaches in the field of education.

3. Training of teachers: Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II focused on training teachers with modern knowledge to teach in schools of the new method. According to him, it was necessary not to be limited to traditional religious education, but to teach and promote modern sciences. For this purpose, he sent some teachers to other regions, including Bukhara and Samarkand, and made it possible for them to acquire modern knowledge.

4. Popularization of education: Feruz's reforms in the field of education were not limited to the upper classes but to the general public. The schools established on his initiative were open to everyone, which served to increase the level of literacy and develop the intellectual potential of society. At the same time, science and culture in Khorezm were encouraged to reach a new level by popularizing education.

5. Encouraging education through poetry and literature: Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II created under his pseudonym "Feruz" and tried to arouse interest in science and enlightenment in the society through poetry. His poems reflect the importance of education and enlightenment, encouraging the people

to strive for knowledge and appreciate it. This served to change the attitude of the people towards science and education in a positive direction.

Feruz Khan's progress in education continued even after the Russian invasion in 1873. Especially the jaded schools of Ismail Gaspirali, which started in Crimea, after learning about the teaching system in them, he expressed his desire to establish these educational institutions in Khorezm [9, p. 122].

As a result of Feruz's reforms in the field of education, a favorable environment was created for the formation and development of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm. His activities in this regard had a positive effect on the spread of enlightenment ideas in other regions of Central Asia at that time. Therefore, the educational reforms of Mohammad Rakhim Khan II made a great contribution to the educational and cultural development not only of Khorezm, but also of the entire region.

Literature analysis (review):

Scientific studies on the role of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II (Feruz) in the emergence of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm are rich and diverse from the point of view of historiography and literary studies. On the basis of the research conducted on this topic, the formation of the Jadidism movement, its social, political and cultural factors, as well as the activities of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II were deeply analyzed.

Initially, when historians of Uzbekistan studied the socio-political history of Khorezm in the 19th century, Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II's attitude and influence on the Jadidist movement was particularly noteworthy. Sh. In the works of researchers such as Shomukhamedov[10], S. Niyazov[7], the beginning process of the modernist movement in Khorezm and the influence of socio-political conditions on its development were studied. In their works, it is emphasized that the reforms of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II as a ruler, especially his approach to culture and enlightenment, created a foundation for the emergence of new ideas and views in society.

In the works of scientists such as N. Torakulov[5], Kh. Bobojonov[3], based on the research of historical sources and documents, the changes made in the field of education during the time of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II were analyzed in detail. They studied the khan's attention to opening new method schools, his motivation to teach secular subjects in these schools, and shed light on his influence on the Jadidist movement. Especially in these sources, it is shown that Feruz's policy aimed at supporting science and enlightenment, served the

intellectual development of the society. In this respect, researchers describe Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II as a progressive thinking statesman of his time.

Within the framework of literary studies, it has been written that the personal literary heritage of Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II, especially his poems written under the pseudonym "Feruz", were of great importance in the formation of Jadidism ideas. In the scientific articles of scientists such as A. Akhmedov[1], S. Azizov[2], Feruz's poetic work, topics aimed at raising enlightenment and moral values were analyzed. According to them, Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II called the people to strive for knowledge, culture and innovation through his poems and literary work. These scientific works prove that Feruz created a spiritual ground for the Jadidism movement.

There are also scientific studies on the historical development of the Jadidism movement in Khorezm, the intellectuals who supported it, and the impact of this movement on the education system of the country. For example, in the researches of M. Olimov[6], H. Ibragimov[4], the reforms of Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II in the field of culture and education and the impact of these reforms on the social development of Khorezm are highlighted. They think that as a result of the khan's initiatives, secular sciences were taught in new schools and madrasas along with religious sciences, which encouraged a new way of thinking in society.

In general, the analysis of the literature shows that the activities and reforms of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II are considered an important factor in the emergence of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm. Researches dedicated to him introduce Mukhammad Rakhimkhan II with his actions and reforms in the field of culture and education, describing him as an advanced representative of modernist ideas. On the basis of these scientific works, the influence of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II on the formation and development of the Jadidism movement in Khorezm is sufficiently covered, and the research conducted in this regard provides the scientific justification of the topic.

Conclusion:

The role and influence of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II (Feruz) in the formation of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm becomes clearer through a deeper analysis of historical processes. In the second half of the 19th century, the Khanate of Khiva aspired to social, cultural and educational changes and showed openness to new thoughts and ideas. These changes were largely the result of the educational activities and reforms of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II.

The results show that Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II implemented a number of reforms aimed at the development of culture and education in the country during his reign. He created important conditions for the Jadidism movement in Khorezm, paying attention to the opening of new method schools, the establishment of modern libraries, and the introduction of the system of teaching secular sciences. The introduction of a new method of education, which is one of the main principles of this movement, served to form a new generation of intellectuals in Khorezm.

The analysis of the literature shows that Feruz's educational activity was closely related to his personal literary work and the new values he brought to the society. Through his poems and literary work, he called the society to knowledge and encouraged the people to think in a new way. At the same time, Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II, as a forward-thinking statesman of his time, carried out political administration and cultural-educational reforms harmoniously, paving the way for the successful development of the Jadidism movement.

In short, the reforms and initiatives of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II were of great importance in the formation and development of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm. He paved the way for the introduction of new methods and ideas in the spheres of culture and education, and made a great contribution to the formation of a new outlook in society. Feruz's work in this regard created a unique period in the development of science, culture and social development in Khorezm. Therefore, the role and legacy of Mukhammad Rakhim Khan II in the emergence of the Jadidist movement in Khorezm is still a subject worthy of deep scientific study.

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